

REACTION SQUEEZE CAST PROCESSING AND INTERMETALLICS DISPERSED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The new in-situ process, Reaction Squeeze Casting, has been developed by which the intermetallic compounds are dispersed in the aluminum matrix composites to improve the elevated temperature performance. The process conditions were optimized by trial and error. While the conditions to make the sound composites is limited, the short fiber reinforced and intermetallics dispersed aluminum matrix composites have the advantage of strength at elevated temperature by 100°C comparing to the conventional short fiber reinforced composites and have an excellent wear resistivity, which are fabricated by reaction squeeze casting.

KEYWORDS: MMC, reaction, titanium, nickel, squeeze casting, processing, aluminum alloy, intermetallic compounds, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous ceramic fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites decrease extremely in strength at the temperature range exceeding 200°C because of inheriting the matrix strength of aluminum. One of authors reviewed the high temperature performance of SiC and Si₃N₄ whisker reinforced aluminum composites as shown in Fig.1 and 2, respectively[1]. In both figures, there is a steep drop of strength at the temperature exceeding 200°C. This means that it is impossible for us to apply the composites to the structural machine components operating at elevated temperature around 250°C. In order to improve the high temperature strength, the authors have being studied the composites by reaction squeeze casting, whose matrix is strengthened by the dispersed intermetallic compound such as TiAl₃, NiAl₃, FeAl₃. They are produced by reaction between molten aluminum and titanium oxide (TiO₂) and metal powder (Ni,Fe), followed by equation.(1)-(3).

Fig.1 : Effect of matrix alloys, manufacturing process and test temperature on high-temperature tensile strength of SiC whisker reinforced Al alloys. (SQ; Squeeze cast, P/M; Powder metallurgy)

Fig.2 : Effect of matrix alloys, manufacturing process and test temperature on high-temperature tensile strength of Si₃N₄ whisker reinforced Al alloys. (SQ; Squeeze cast, P/M; Powder metallurgy)

Reaction squeeze casting is for the in-situ process to make aluminum matrix strengthened by utilizing the reaction between the oxide or metal powder and molten aluminum, resulting to produce the small intermetallics-dispersed matrix, as well as reinforced by discontinuous ceramic fibers which do not react with the molten aluminum at all. This article offers the processing and properties by summarizing previous papers[10-18].

EXPERIMENTALS

Preparation of preforms

The powder and reinforcement employed in the experiment of reaction squeeze casting are listed in Table 1. The anatase type of TiO₂ powder and whisker, rutile type of TiO₂ powder, Ni and Fe powder were selected as a starting agent, which were reactive with molten aluminum, resulting to intermetallic compounds. Silicon carbide whisker (SiCw) and alumina

Table 1: Properties of powder and reinforcement.

Powder Reinforcement	Diameter μm	Length μm	Density Mg/m ³
TiO ₂ (rutile)	0.2~0.3	-	4.2
TiO ₂ (anatase)	0.3~0.4	-	3.9
TiO ₂ (anatase whisker)	0.5	13	3.9
Ni	3~7	-	8.9
Fe	5~6	-	7.8
SiC whisker	0.2	10~40	3.2
Al ₂ O ₃ fiber	3	150~	3.3

short fiber are also employed as a reinforcement for aluminum matrix, and in some experiments, employed as a reinforcement for powder preforms with small volume fraction of 5 to 15%.

Fig.3 : Preparing process of preform.

Preforms were prepared as shown in Fig.3; adjusting the length of fiber by pressing at 100MPa, mixing them reactive powder in solvent, drying them in electric furnace and finally adjusting their volume fraction to 20-45% by compaction process. Preform size is 44 mm in diameter and 20 mm in height.

Procedure of Reaction Squeeze Casting

The conventional squeeze casting apparatus is outlined in Fig.4. Preform was heated by cylindrical electric furnace to temperature T_p , together with metal die. As soon as molten aluminum at a given temperature, T_m , was poured from the top, punch run down at the speed of 1 cm/s to applied the pressure ranging from 50 to 100 MPa. The pressure were maintained for chill time of 60s. In cases, transient temperature at the center of preform was measured by sheathed thermo-couple of 1.0 mm in sheath diameter as shown in Fig.4 during squeeze casting process.

Fig.4 : Outline of direct squeeze casting apparatus.
 T_m : molten aluminum temperature
 T_p : preform temperature

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the beginning of this study, we repeated various kinds of and large numbers of trial and error shots. An example of the results is shown in Table 2 or 3. Those results are summarized as follows from the view points of productivity and reactivity.

- 1) Preforms consisting of monolithic powder and high volume fraction of TiO₂, Fe or Ni does not make the bulkily and uniformly intermetallics-dispersed MMC, because of severe reaction. It is necessary that one or two kinds of powder are mixed with ceramic reinforcement, preventing the infiltration of molten aluminum from choking out by reaction products.
- 2) Infiltrating length of melt into preform and reactivity of preform with molten aluminum are remarkably dependent on not only T_m and T_a, but also volume fraction of powder, however hardly dependent on final squeeze pressure.
- 3) Anatase type of TiO₂ is more easy to react than rutile type.
- 4) It appears that infiltrating process at molten aluminum front is time dependent and enthalpy dependent process accompanying with exothermic reaction and with heat diffusion.

Table2: An example of trial and error results of reaction squeeze casting for TiO₂+SiCw/Al systems.

No.	Preform Vf, %	T _p °C	T _m °C	Infiltrated length, mm
1	15%TiO ₂ (r)+15%SiCw	410	750	0
2	"	340	810	5
3	"	500	750	11
4	"	500	800	13
5	20%TiO ₂ (r)+10%SiCw	340	760	5
6	"	340	780	6
7	15%TiO ₂ (a)+15%SiCw	500	670	0
8	"	500	800	15
9	"	500	830	13

Final squeeze pressure ; p=100MPa, punch speed ; v=1cm/s, chill time under final pressure ; t=60s.
(r) ; rutile type, (a) ; anatase type

Table3: An example of trial and error results of reaction squeeze casting for TiO₂+SiCw+Ni, Fe/Al systems.

No.	Preform Vf, %	T _p °C	T _m °C	Infiltrated length, mm
1	15%TiO ₂ (r)+15%SiCw+5%Fe	500	770	6
2	"	480	820	20
3	20%TiO ₂ (r)+10%SiCw+5%Fe	500	830	6
4	15%TiO ₂ (a)+15%SiCw+5%Ni	500	800	20
5	15%TiO ₂ (r)+15%SiCw+5%Ni	500	800	20
6	5%TiO ₂ (a)+20%SiCw+5%Ni	400	800	20
7	"	450	800	20
8	5%TiO ₂ (r)+20%SiCw+5%Ni	420	740	20
9	"	450	740	20
10	"	475	740	20
11	"	390	770	16

Final squeeze pressure ; p=100MPa, punch speed ; v=1cm/s, chill time under final pressure ; t=60s.
(r) ; rutile type, (a) ; anatase type

Effect of Preform Temperature and Molten Aluminum Temperature

Figure 5 shows the effect of preform temperature (T_p) and molten aluminum temperature (T_m) on infiltration and reactivity when molten pure aluminum forced to infiltrate into the preform with 5% TiO_2 +5% Ni+20%SiCw (volumetric percent) at punch speed 1 cm/s under final squeeze pressure 50 Mpa. The dotted line shows the resultant temperature $T_n = 660^\circ C$ determined by equation (4).

$$T_n = (T_m \cdot V_m \cdot C_{pm} \cdot \rho_m + T_p \cdot V_f \cdot C_{pf} \cdot \rho_f) / (V_m \cdot C_{pm} \cdot \rho_m + V_f \cdot C_{pf} \cdot \rho_f) \quad (4)$$

Where, V_m, V_f : volume fraction of matrix and fiber
 C_{pm}, C_{pf} : specific heat of matrix and fiber
 ρ_m, ρ_f : specific density of matrix and fiber

Fig.5 : Effect of molten aluminum and preform temperature on the infiltration and reaction when squeeze-cast to the preform of 20%SiCw+ 5% TiO_2 + 5%Ni.

It is the sufficient condition for full infiltration that T_p and T_m make the resultant temperature higher than melting temperature of aluminum. From the experiment full infiltration and sufficient reaction still achieved enough under the temperature $T_n = 660^\circ C$, when the temperature difference between T_p and T_m becomes small. The reason may explained by small amounts of heat loss and heat generation by exothermic reaction.

Effect of Powder Diameter

The hardness of composites increased when TiO_2 powders in preform react with aluminum, resulting to produce titanium aluminides and Al_2O_3 . Effect of mean diameter of TiO_2 powder on the hardness of composites is shown in Fig.6. The hardness increases with decrease in diameter. The hardness is raised remarkably to Hv850, by employing $0.4\mu m$ in diameter, however there is no hardness raise in the case of $11.8\mu m$ in diameter, at the same volume fraction of TiO_2 . An analysis of X-ray diffraction patterns of the composites employed 0.4 and

11.8 μ m powder are shown in Fig.7. The composites of 0.4 μ m TiO₂ powder consist of Al₂O₃ (Hv=1600-1700), TiAl₃ (Hv=400-700) and Ti₃Al. On the other hand, the composites of 11.8 μ m TiO₂ powder consist of merely Al and TiO₂. That is, the reaction did not finish yet, because the surface area of 11.8 μ m TiO₂ powder is so small comparing to that of 0.4 μ m TiO₂ powder under a certain volume fraction of preform.

Fig. 6 : Effect of mean diameter of TiO₂ powder on hardness of composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting with use of molten aluminum under constant volume fraction of preform.

Fig.7 : X-ray diffraction patterns of composites, fabricated by reaction squeeze casting employed molten aluminum and 45% TiO₂ preform. ($T_m=800^\circ\text{C}$, $T_p=450^\circ\text{C}$, $p=50\text{Mpa}$, $v=1\text{cm/s}$)

Effect of Volume Fraction

Figure 8 shows the effect of volume fraction of TiO₂ powder and TiO₂ whisker on the hardness of MMC, fabricated by reaction squeeze casting, which is also reinforced by a certain

Fig. 8 : Effect of volume fraction of TiO₂ on hardness of composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting employed molten aluminum, whisker and powder type TiO₂ preform.

Fig. 10: Effect of volume fraction of Ni and Fe powders on hardness of the Composites with 20% SiCw+Ni or Fe powder. ($T_m=750^\circ\text{C}$, $T_p=350^\circ\text{C}$, $p=100\text{MPa}$, $v=1\text{cm/s}$, $t=60\text{s}$)

volume percent of Al₂O₃ fiber. As the volume fraction of TiO₂ increases, the hardness slightly increased, too. The effect is characterized by that the hardness is raised from Hv200 to Hv750 abruptly when volume fraction reaches to the range from 25% to 30%. There is the critical volume fraction for the synthesis of reaction. The flash temperature determined by heat generation and heat exchange per unit volume may control the synthesis proceed or not. It appears that ignition temperature is. The temperature-time curve at the center of preform are illustrated in Fig.9. There can be seen the great difference in maximum temperature between 20% and 25% of TiO₂ whisker addition.

Fig.9 : Time-Temperature curve of preform with 25% and 20%TiO₂+15%Al₂O₃ infiltrated by molten aluminum in reaction squeeze casting process.

Figure 10 shows the micro vickers hardness of MMCs fabricated by reaction squeeze casting in which the preforms consisting of 20% SiC whisker and variable volume fraction of Fe or Ni powder are prepared. The hardness increases with addition of Fe and Ni powder, because they result to become intermetallic compounds by reacting with molten aluminum within about 20 seconds under the pressure 100MPa, before melt is solidified. The microstructures are uniform in the order of the original powder size.

Processing Guide Line

We have induced the processing guide from various kinds of experiments and analysis as follows.

- 1) Reaction squeeze casting is, in the moving boundary process of transient reactive band.
- 2) The best process condition for fabricating the bulky MMC and for producing uniformly intermetallics-dispersed matrix, is as follows: the reaction synthesis proceeds in seconds after molten aluminum finishes to infiltrate to the bottom of preform.
- 3)As for as TiO₂ powder 0.4 μm in diameter, the hardness of aluminum matrix composites

are controlled up to Hv300 by reaction squeeze casting, however it is difficult to produce the composites more than Hv800 in hardness and 15 mm in thickness.

4) Heat treatment is excellent process to control the hardness of composite, after the insufficiently reacted composites have been fabricated.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The dispersion of reaction products such as Al₂O₃, TiAl₃, NiAl₃ is effective for improving the matrix strength at elevated temperatures and wear resistance of MMC. Figure 11 shows the high temperature strength of the MMC as cast which is fabricated by reaction squeeze casting, employing the preform of 20% SiCw+5%TiO₂+5%Ni and molten aluminum. In the figure, the new composites are compared to the conventional 20%SiCw/Al composites. The new MMC keeps still 320MPa of bending strength at 400°C while the conventional one bears merely against 90 MPa. The advantage of strength offers the application for the structural component of machine operating at elevated temperature 350°C. Figure 12 [17] and Table 4 [18] demonstrate the wear resistivity of MMCs fabricated by reaction squeeze casting. The minute examination into the test pieces shows that the excellent wear resistivity comes from the dispersion of intermetallics in the aluminum matrix.

Table 4 : Built in wear test of piston manufactured by reaction squeeze casting.

Piston materials	Wear, mg
AC8A.Aluminum alloy,T6	4020
Niresist cast iron	460
12%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	77
5%TiO ₂ whisker+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	30
10%TiO ₂ whisker+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	31
5%TiO ₂ powder+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	51
10%TiO ₂ powder+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	45

Oil temperature; 250 °C, Pulsating load; 6MPa, frequency; 20Hz, 300hrs

Fig.11: Comparison of bending strength at elevated temperatures between conventional composites and intermetallics dispersed composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting

Fig.12 : Comparison of wear resistivity between conventional materials and intermetallics dispersed composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting.

CONCLUSION

Reaction squeeze casting is a kind of transient process, and a limited condition leads to success to fabricate the bulky and uniform-structured composites. Preparing the preform is another key point, which consists of the discontinuous ceramic fibers, fine oxides and metal powders. It is important that preform and molten aluminum temperature during the process are selected so that the resultant temperature calculated by the rule of energy conservation is nearly liquidus temperature of aluminum.

The intermetallics-dispersed aluminum matrix composites offers an excellent strength at elevated temperatures and wear resistivity subjected to sliding and fretting load.

The process is promising to use practically for wide applications, such as piston, cylinder, cylinder head, vane pump and so on.

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